

belowground (root) portions of *Sesbania aculeata* to wetland rice and the effect of green manure and a nonleguminous crop fortified with fertilizer N on yield and N uptake of rice.

Soil was calcareous sandy loam with pH 8.2, 0.37% organic C, and 0.08% total N. The experiment, conducted during 1987 wet season, was in a randomized complete block design with three replications. The 12 treatments comprising green manure and urea N are described in the table.

Sesbania and maize crops grown for 51 d were incorporated 1 d before transplanting rice. Sesbania accumulated 4.1 t dry matter and 125 kg N/ha. Maize accumulated 1.64 t dry matter and 20.7 kg N/ha. Long-duration rice PR108 was transplanted 27 Jun 1987 in 23.4-m² plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing. N as urea was applied in 2 equal splits — 21 and 42 d after transplanting (DT) — in green manure plots and in 3 equal splits — 7, 21, and 42 DT — in fallow and maize plots. All plots received 26 kg P and 25 kg K/ha at final puddling.

At 35 DT, dry matter and N uptake of rice were significantly higher in plots fertilized with sesbania or urea. The plots receiving belowground portion of sesbania showed no significant gain over fallow plots. In maize plots, growth and N uptake of rice did not differ significantly from those in fallow plots. Without green manure, rice responded up to 180 kg N/ha. Incorporating sesbania produced yields equivalent to those with 120 kg N/ha. This shows that efficiency of N contained in sesbania is similar to that of urea N.

Yields from plots green manured with sesbania shoots did not differ significantly from those with sesbania grown and buried *in situ*. This suggests that the mineralizable N in sesbania is contained mainly in the aboveground portions. Yield from plots from which sesbania shoots were removed did not differ significantly from yield in fallow plots.

Without fertilizer N, incorporation of the maize crop containing 1.26% N did not prove beneficial. With 60 kg N/ha,

Effect of green manure and N level on growth and N uptake of rice. Ludhiana, India, 1987 wet season.

Treatment		Dry matter at 35 DT (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	N uptake (kg/ha)		Apparent N recovery ^a (%)
Green manure	Urea N (kg/ha)			35 DT	Maturity	
Sesbania grown and incorporated	0	1.8	7.6	31	133	41.6
	60	2.3	8.7	41	164	51.7 ^b
Sesbania grown and aboveground portion removed	0	1.2	5.3	19	86	—
	60	1.5	6.5	26	111	41.7 ^b
Sesbania not grown but aboveground portion from preceding treatment incorporated	0	1.9	7.4	28	134	42.4
	60	2.2	9.0	36	170	60.0 ^b
Maize grown and incorporated	0	1.1	5.4	17	89	38.1
	60	1.6	7.9	26	149	100.0 ^b
Fallow	0	1.2	5.0	18	81	—
	60	1.6	6.2	26	109	46.7
	120	1.9	7.5	33	141	50.0
	180	2.0	8.6	38	174	51.7
LSD		0.39	0.81	5.1	11.6	—

^aApparent N recovery of green manure N was calculated by subtracting N uptake in no-N control of fallow treatment. ^bValue corresponding to apparent N recovery for 60 kg N/ha in the presence of green manure.

maize-incorporated plots produced spectacularly high rice yields, equal to those with 120 kg N/ha. Total N uptake of rice at maturity showed a similar pattern.

Apparent recovery of fertilizer N was about 50% in fallow plots and 40% from

plots with N applied as green manure. Apparent recovery of fertilizer N in maize plots was surprisingly high. It seems that N applied in maize plots narrowed the C:N of maize residue, which then behaved as a slow-release fertilizer. □

Azolla growth under different rice planting methods in Kerala

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A study of the effect of rice planting method on azolla growth during 1980 dry season (Sep-Jan) and 1981 wet season (Jun-Sep) showed that the bulk planting method favored maximum azolla growth. We conducted a more extensive trial during 1981 dry season to confirm this finding.

Yields of azolla and rice as affected by method of planting rice. Pattambi, India, 1981 dry season.

Planting method	Azolla yield (g/m ²) 3 wk after inoculation	Rice yield (t/ha)	
		Grain	Straw
20 × 10 cm east-west direction	182	4.8	3.3
20 × 10 cm north-south direction	179	4.7	3.1
40 × 5 cm east-west direction	160	4.3	3.1
40 × 5 cm north-south direction	181	4.6	3.4
Bulk method (equidistant, 50 hills/m ²)	191	4.1	3.0
Fallow (without rice)	68	—	—
LSD (0.05)	15	ns	ns

Growth of azolla (g/m²)

Mean water temperature (°C 1400 h)

Daily mean light intensity (Klx) below the canopy

--- P1 - 20 x 10 cm East-west
 --- P2 - 20 x 10 cm North-south
 --- P3 - 40 x 5 cm East-west
 --- P4 - 40 x 5 cm North-south
 --- P5 - Bulk method
 --- P6 - Fallow

Effect of rice planting method on azolla growth, in relation to water temperature and light intensity. Pattambi, Kerala, India, 1981 dry season.

Line plantings with two spacing combinations and two directions of lines were compared with equidistant planting (bulk method) to assure equal plant populations per unit area. Azolla was inoculated at 100 g/m² 1 wk after planting rice; azolla yield was measured 3 wk after inoculation.

Azolla growth was maximum with the bulk rice planting method (see table). That method registered the highest light interception and lowest water temperature (see figure). Planting method did not influence rice grain and straw yields. □

Green manure as N source for flooded rice

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N content and rate of mineralization determine the efficiency of a green manure. Leguminous crops used as green manure differ in both respects. We evaluated *Sesbania aculeata*, sunn hemp (*Crotalaria juncea*), cowpea (*Vigna*

unguiculata), and cluster bean (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*) as green manure for flooded rice.

Soil was a sandy loam, with pH 8.2, 0.34% organic C, and 0.06% total N. A basal dose of 26 kg P/ha as single superphosphate and 25 kg K/ha as muriate of potash was applied before the last puddling.

Green manure crops were incorporated at 60 d, 1 d before transplanting long-duration rice variety PR106 at 15- × 20-cm spacing.

Yield (t/ha)

N uptake (kg/ha)

Apparent N recovery (%)

Source and rate (kg/ha) of N

Influence of N through green manure on grain yield, N uptake, and apparent N recovery by rice, Ludhiana, India. Bars having a common letter are not significantly different.

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